

Chromosome constitution of three monotelosomic and one monoacrocentric alien addition lines of rice each carrying a telocentric or acrocentric single chromosome of *O. punctata*. Mitotic chromosomes of MtAAL 2 (a), MaAAL 4S4L (b), and MtAAL 7(c), and meiotic chromosomes of MtAAL 9S (d and e). Each arrow indicates the telocentric and/or acrocentric chromosomes derived from *O. punctata*.

MAALs or Mt(a)AALs (approximately 0%). The telocentric and acrocentric chromosomes would originate from a misdivision of an alien chromosome and the following chromosome breakage in the PMCs of the respective MAALs at the first or second anaphase. The addition lines with small chromosomal fragments such as alien telocentric and acrocentric chromosomes will serve as a source to transfer useful genes from wild relatives to cultivated rice.

Reference

Yasui H, Iwata N. 1991. Production of monosomic alien addition lines of *Oryza sativa* having a single *O. punctata* chromosome. In: Rice genetics II. Proceedings of the Second International Rice Genetics Symposium, 14-18 May 1990. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. p 147-155. ■

Genetic, histological, and histochemical evidence for reversion to partial fertility in WA CMS line IR54752A

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The widely used wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line IR54752A for the hybrid rice program at IRRI and in India was reported to be unstable for male sterility characters and therefore restricted to use in seed production. We investigated the causes for the breakdown in sterility. All evidence gathered suggested the presence of multiple nuclear genes (minor) for fertility in the CMS line. Evidence included the presence of partially fertile plants in a cross with the isonuclear maintainer line, genetic studies using selfed and test-crossed progenies of the partially fertile plants, and the comparative ease of restoration of fertility of this CMS line in crosses with restorers

as well as maintainer lines of other CMS lines belonging to the same cytoplasmic source. Histological studies revealed normal behavior and functioning of anther wall tissues, including tapetum and endothecium, as well as normal development of microspores in CMS line IR54752A up to the liberation of microspores. The CMS pollen grains differed from other fertile pollen in histochemical components such as starch, proteins, and RNA at maturity, indicating that mobilization of metabolites to the pollen grains was hindered to some extent at maturity. This showed that factors within the microspore were responsible for the breakdown in sterility in IR54752A. ■

Genetics of the thermosensitive genic male sterility trait in rice

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UPRI 95-140 (P1), the thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) line of low-temperature fertility transformation type, was analyzed for its inheritance and transformation behavior. Parents, F_1 , F_2 , and six test crosses between TGMS (female parent) and UPR1 95-141 (P2), UPR1 95-165 (P3), UPR1 95-124 (P4), UPR1 95-117 (P5), and IR36 (P6)

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.